

Research Article

Calculating Comfort Indexes and Applying Comfort Models to Predict Thermal Sensation Vote in Sports Centres

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Predicting the indoor thermal comfort of people while doing sports might pose challenges, as the combination of high metabolic rate, increased humidity of the space due to physical exercise, and the alternate of more and less intense tasks influence perception. This paper is aimed at comparing environmental data (temperature and relative humidity) and calculating comfort indexes (heat index) and two comfort models (Fanger's predicted mean value and the adaptive thermal comfort model) with people's perceptions of the environment. Indoor environmental data for the analysis were collected by monitoring several rooms in eight sports centres in a Mediterranean climate. The thermal sensation votes (TSVs) of the occupants were obtained through an online survey. A detailed explanation of the methodology of the monitoring, creation, and management of the survey and the tools used to analyse the data is provided. Results compare the relation between the TSV and the parameters or indexes calculated. Fanger's predicted mean vote (PMV) model is not able to correctly predict people's sensations, neither for low nor for high metabolic rates. Finally, the neutral temperature of the adaptive model for the studied conditions is calculated. Among the studied parameters and indices, temperature exhibits the strongest correlation with the thermal sensation of the occupants. However, occupants did not report a significant sensation regarding humidity in accordance with the objective conditions of the rooms. The heat index also did not show any significant correlation with the TSV. Nevertheless, across a wide range of conditions, including variations in metabolic activities, temperature, and relative humidity, the percentage of thermal dissatisfaction (indicated by "very hot" responses) remains consistently high. Notably, the temperature at which a peak in neutral sensation can be achieved is less than 21° for low metabolic rate activities.

Keywords: environmental monitoring; high-metabolic activities; indoor environmental quality; postoccupancy evaluation; sports centres; thermal comfort

1. Introduction

Thermal comfort is defined by Fanger [1] as the condition in which the occupant shows a good level of satisfaction with the thermal environment. In the field of indoor environmental quality (IEQ), thermal comfort has been deeply investigated in various types of buildings, including offices and hospitals and educational and residential buildings. Among other types of buildings, sports centres play an important role in our societies. In Spain in 2020, the country where the research took place, six out of 10 people above 15 years old practised some

kind of sport, either periodically or occasionally [2]. Additionally, a large quantity does some kind of guided activities, which are normally carried out inside rooms in sports centres [3]. The community uses buildings dedicated to sports not only for recreation but also for health purposes. Increasing public inclination towards fitness and IEQ of sports buildings is the reason for researching more in this field. People doing high-metabolic activities are more exposed to inhaling pollutants or suffering heat stroke due to raised temperature [4].

Postoccupancy evaluations (POEs) are a useful tool for gathering data from both the building and users' perceptions

of the environmental conditions inside. They can include questions about health, safety, security, functionality, efficiency, satisfaction, etc. [5]. In particular, they allow us to identify the most suitable comfort range for a specific space [6].

Indeed, while in the past, aspects related to the design of the thermal behaviour of buildings were mostly done by applying a physically based determinism, the last decade's field studies showed a few limits to the applicability of such models [7]. The most important one, and still widely used, is the predictive mean vote model by Fanger [8], adopted by many international standards and guidelines such as ISO 7730, ASHRAE Standard 55, and CEN CR 1752 [9]. This model was first developed and intended for artificial climates in controlled spaces only. Nevertheless, it has been applied to more types of buildings in different conditions (such as free running and natural ventilation). Among the first to examine the model, Howell and Kennedy [10] compared the results of Fanger's predictive equation with the thermal sensation obtained in a variety of field settings. They conclude that Fanger's equation and its derivatives provide only a first approximation to the prediction of thermal comfort in "natural" settings. The model does not consider all the factors that have a role in the thermal sensation of people. Psychological variables, like the natural inclination to see oneself as warm- or cold-natured, are among the key factors. Croome [11] proposes that the PMV model underestimates thermal impressions and downplays the fluctuations in this perception because of the assumption of steady-state laboratory conditions (in the development of this model), oversimplified metabolic rates, and the PMV's sensitivity to clothing values.

Research demonstrated that the PMV-predicted neutral temperature can be different from the real preferred one of occupants [12]. Additionally, studies replicated on different continents or countries led to different results [9]. Because of this gap between Fanger's model and the results of experiments, a new type of thermal comfort model started being developed, the so-called adaptive thermal model by Brager and De Dear. The core concept of this model posits that thermal adaptation within constructed surroundings can be ascribed to three distinct processes: behavioural modification, physiological acclimatization, and psychological expectation [13]. After its first publication, a big quantum of knowledge has been produced by other researchers who replicated the study and applied the methods to other databases. So far, it has not been possible to close this scissor between the PMV model and adaptive model results [14]. According to De Dear et al. [15], the focus should be on finding an evidence-based parameterisation of the concept of comfort expectation.

There are many examples of studies in the literature using POE for determining thermal comfort. Among them, Li et al. [14] used a database of environmental data and subjective thermal sensations of occupants collected in Australia to estimate long-term thermal comfort. They calculated a variety of physical indices and compared them to the subjective index of long-term thermal comfort using Pearson's correlation analysis. Others, like Shawesh and Mohamed [16], collected data themselves from a case study in Saudi Arabia.

Subjective assessment included a special parameter called "physiological equivalent temperature" (PET) and PMV, and the results of online and self-directed questionnaires were compared to measurements of environmental parameters. POE studies can also be related to specific parts of buildings with peculiar conditions, such as the kitchens of restaurants and canteens. The work of Alam, Sharma, and Salve [17] focuses on this case, as the hot and humid conditions in kitchens can harm the health and productivity of cooking staff, potentially affecting their comfort and work quality as the day goes on. During the investigation, they found out that 88% of the cooking workers were not satisfied with the thermal environment. A similar study involves kitchens on Indian trains, proving that thermal comfort is not only relevant in the classical built environment but also in transport [18]. The findings suggest that the PMV model may not be suitable for assessing thermal comfort in pantry car kitchens on railways. Furthermore, they determined that the neutral temperature for workers in summer and winter was 23°C and 21.62°C, respectively.

When focusing on POE about sports buildings, it is still possible to find relevant studies, but Işıklar Bengi and Topraklı [19] highlight the deficiency of this kind of study about sports buildings. Huang et al. [6] carried out a POE of five sports buildings in China under hot and humid climatic conditions. They made use of measurements of thermal, acoustic, and visual comfort and indoor air quality and the responses of more than 300 exercisers. Ortiz et al. [20] evaluated the environmental comfort of the athletes and spectators in a nZEB (nearly zero energy building) pavilion in Spain by making measurements of the visual and thermal comfort and the air quality by making surveys of the audience. Revel and Arnesano reported in different works [21, 22] a monitoring methodology for thermal comfort through smart metering and the handling of a survey of the occupants. A comparison is made between standardised and subjective measurements to assess the impact of the activity rate and clothing on systematic errors in the evaluation of comfort using Fanger's indices. The case study is a sports centre in Italy.

When it comes to comfort models specifically for sports centres, it should be noted that there are no clear, established guidelines on measuring thermal comfort in these kinds of facilities [23]. Indeed, neither the PMV nor the adaptive models are conceived to be for discontinuous activities with high metabolic rates typical of these buildings.

The main objective of the present study is to compare the thermal sensation votes (TSVs) collected between occupants with the objective data monitored and the results of different comfort models in the peculiar conditions of the weight and fitness rooms of sports centres. Additionally, the neutral temperature for rooms in sports centres will be calculated. The study is aimed at bridging the gap between thermal comfort models and their applications in sports buildings. The final goal is to obtain which are the best environmental conditions for users to satisfy the highest number of occupants. At the same time, it will contribute to a more conscious use of the HVAC system of the sports centres, therefore reducing energy consumption.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design of the Monitoring Campaigns. The first part of the study consisted of the preparation of a monitoring campaign in several sports centres to set up a database of environmental data for further analysis. Data collection was performed between November 2022 and July 2023 in the province of Barcelona, Spain, therefore collecting information from three different climatic seasons: winter, summer, and an intermediate season we will call “swing season” (which is included in winter for similarity of conditions of temperature and relative humidity). Besides small local differences, all the buildings benefit from a Hot-summer Mediterranean climate (Csa) according to the Koppen–Geiger climate classification [24], with hot dry summers and mild to cool winters. Eight different sports centres were involved in the study, allowing the monitoring of different types of rooms. The number of monitored rooms for items of research can be found in Table 1. To avoid any misunderstanding among readers about the types of rooms, a brief description of each is provided below:

- Weight rooms are the rooms used for weightlifting, calisthenics, and sometimes guided activities in small groups. These kinds of rooms usually have machinery for exercising specific muscle groups (chest press, leg press, lat pull-down, leg extension, seated row and smith machines, and cable machines) and equipment such as free weights (kettlebells, dumbbells, barbells, and weight plates), plyometric boxes, resistance bands, and medicine balls, as well as machinery for cardiovascular exercises such as treadmills, stationary bicycles, and elliptical trainers. In this kind of room, occupants are often performing diverse physical activities at the same time, alternating moments of intense stress with breaks.
- Group fitness rooms are those rooms used for different types of activities, mostly done in groups under the guidance of an instructor. The activity can be of any type, from yoga to Zumba, but the common characteristic is that all the occupants are doing the same thing at the same time.
- Spinning rooms are rooms with only stationary bikes which can be used individually and for group classes.

A wide variety of activities have been performed in the rooms during the monitoring period. Therefore, very different conditions have been detected, from low metabolic intensity to very high ones. A list of all the activities monitored is reported in Table 2. Information on the metabolic activity for each one of the activities has been retrieved from the Compendium of Physical Activities of the American College of Sports Medicine [25, 26] by referring to the most similar one, or exactly to the right one. Activities with less than four MET and the general sports activity done in the weight room are considered low-intensity ones (called FITLOW), while activities with an equal or higher MET than four are called high-metabolic activities (called HIGH), according to the definition proposed by ASHRAE 55 2020.

TABLE 1: Number of rooms monitored across the eight monitored sports centres for type and season.

Type of room	Total	Winter	Swing season	Summer
Weight room	8	2	3	3
Group fitness rooms	10	3	5	2
Spinning rooms	4	1	2	1

Therefore, activities with an associated MET lower than four and the general sports activity done in the weight room are called FITLOW, while all those activities with a metabolic rate equal to or higher than four are called HIGH.

The duration of each monitoring was fixed to 2 weeks to balance the need for having a more representative sample of data (e.g., avoiding the presence of festivities could compromise having realistic data for each day of the week).

2.2. Data Collection. The indoor environmental parameters monitored include air temperature and relative humidity. In the sports centres, the sensors used to record those data were the Comet U3430 (Comet) model. The recording interval was set to 2 min. These kinds of sensors are small and have a long battery duration, making transportation and frequent changes of location throughout the monitoring campaign easy. The technical data is shown in Table 3. The whole data collection methodology of data has been done in accordance with the one used by Alegría-Sala et al. [27] and other researchers in the field such as Alam, Muthiah, and Salve [18, 28]. They used to leave the sensors in the monitored spaces for the period of the monitoring. Each parameter’s value was based on the average sensor readings, and there were no changes to the usual classroom conditions. Ventilation, conditioning, clothing, and occupant behaviour remained unchanged throughout the experiment.

It has to be mentioned that performing data recording in spaces which are used daily by several different people (who are not always well aware of the research going on) and doing physical activities can be challenging. Sensors cannot always be placed at the most optimal point for research purposes, as they cannot occupy space for the users. Therefore, the placement of sensors has been specifically selected for every room monitored, together with the opinion of the managers of the facilities. In any case, a few general rules have been followed, according to the recommendations of ASHRAE 55 [29]:

- Sensors were placed, as much as possible, in the range of 1–2 m of height (considering that ASHRAE suggests taking measures at 1.1 and 1.7 m for standing occupants).
- Points of local injection of air must be avoided, as well as direct solar radiation.
- In the case of rooms with more floors, a sensor has to be placed on every one of them.
- If possible, a minimum of two sensors must be placed in every monitored room, in different positions.

TABLE 2: List of all the activities detected in the monitored sports centres, divided by metabolic intensity, with code reference to the Compendium of Physical Activities by the American Society of Sports Medicine [25].

Low metabolic activities			High-metabolic activities		
Name	MET	CPA ref.	Name	MET	CPA ref.
Pilates	3	02105	Zumba	7.2	02005
Body balance	2.5	02105	Dancing	7.2	02005
Yoga	2.5	02105	Spinning	7	02010
Hypopressives	2.5	02105	Body core (Les Mills)	6.8	02110
Stretching	2.3	02101	GAC	6.8	02110
			STEP	6.8	02110
			Aerobic	6.8	02110
			Best training	6	02146
			Body pump	6	02146
			4Functional	6	02146
			Body combat	5.3	15425
			Cardio	4	02143
			Tone	4	02143
			Karate	10.3	15430
			Functional circuit	8	02040
			Functional training	8	02040
			Fitbox	10.3	15430
			Cool	10.3	15430

TABLE 3: Technical specification of the Comet U3430 sensor.

	Measuring range	Resolution	Accuracy
Air temp. (°C)	-20 ÷ 60	0.1	± 0.4
Relative humidity (%)	0 ÷ 100	0.1	± 1.8

- Sensors in the same room must be placed as far as possible to capture an average of the room condition and possible differences between points.
- The minimum distance between two sensors has to be at least 3 m.
- Sensors were not moved during the whole duration of the test.

Additionally, data on the occupation of the rooms were collected, i.e., the number of occupants in each one of the rooms during the activities. This kind of data was either shared by the sports centres, which usually have it because activities/classes have to be booked in advance through an app or a website, or because trainers have to keep a record of how many users are actually coming to their classes. In case this was not available, we placed sensors of the brand Eastek, model Peoplecounter Counteasy USB V3. This sensor is made up of two parts which are usually placed on the opposite walls of a corridor or at the entrance of a room so that they can count the passage of people through it. Data was collected with hourly detail. In this case, not even placing sensors were possible, and moments of occupation were

TABLE 4: Technical specification of the Anemometer PCE-009.

	Measuring range	Resolution	Accuracy
Airspeed (m/s)	0.2 ÷ 20	0.1	± (5% + 0.1 m/s) for measurement or ± (1% + 0.1 m/s) for complete scale

TABLE 5: Number of useful answers registered for every type of activity and season (winter includes swing season).

Season	FITLOW	HIGH	Total
Winter	105	15	120
Summer	79	21	100
Total	184	36	220

extracted from schedules of the activities of the sports centres and just flagged as “occupation time,” without additional information on the number of people. These data have been adjusted to have hourly detail. Through calendars of the sports facilities, it was also noted down the type of activity practised in every occupied moment.

During monitoring campaigns, the research team took punctual measures of the airspeed in the monitored rooms. Measurements have been made with a hot-wire anemometer at a height of 1.1 m (the medium height suggested by ASHRAE 55 [29]) in different and uniformly spaced points inside the monitored rooms, far enough from windows and air

FIGURE 1: Blue dots represent the plotting of TSV against the temperature measured. Each graph corresponds to a different group of answers. The straight lines are the linear correlations between the TSV and temperature in each case. The red-shaded area is the 95% confidence band.

ducts. They never overpassed the value of 0.2 m/s. The technical data is shown in Table 4.

The objective data collection has been complemented by the sensation of people about IEQ through an online survey with the free tool Microsoft Forms. Posters with a QR code were hung up on the walls and doors of the occupied rooms. Occupants were therefore able to access the online questionnaire by scanning it with their smartphones. The survey was composed of a brief number of questions to be filled out in a short period. Answers were completely anonymous, as no personal data was asked but the thermal, humidity, and air quality sensations. The thermal sensation was asked using the ASHRAE [29] seven-point thermal sensation scale. Humidity sensation makes use of a five-point sensation scale and air quality a three-point one. An additional question required indicating the clothes they were using to get an estimation of the clothing level. Indeed, each of the elements of the list (socks, underwear, shorts, top, etc.) was connected to a value of clo and allowed calculating the total clo of that interviewee. More details on the questions made can be found in the Appendix. Two hundred thirty answers were collected throughout the whole campaign, but only 220 were completed. Table 5 lists the number of answers collected for each category of data.

2.3. Data Analysis. Recorded data from each sports centre (temperature, relative humidity, occupation, and type of

activity) and the questionnaire's answers were analysed with the Python libraries PsychroLib [30], NumPy [31], Pandas, and sklearn.linear_model [32] for the linear regression and Matplotlib for data visualization.

First, the data were checked to filter out all those moments without occupation. Then, temperature, relative humidity, and CO₂ concentration are linked to the occupation and activity schedule of the room. Then, to perform a comparison between the answers to the survey and the objective data, each answer is linked to the environmental conditions in the room at the moment of the submission of the questionnaire. The heat index has been calculated using the equation used by the National Weather Service of the United States by Rothfus [33] for temperature in Celsius degrees. The PMV has been calculated with the Python library pythermalcomfort [34] by using the ASHRAE 55 standard 2020 [29]. Clothing is set to 0.3 clo as it is the average of clothing levels used by occupants, as collected through the survey. The metabolic rate was differentiated depending on whether it was FITLOW or HIGH. FITLOW's metabolic rate was set to 2.5, as it was the most common MET value according to Table 2. HIGH instead was set at 6.8 MET as it was the central value in the normal distribution of the metabolic rates indicated in Column 2 of Table 2. To be able to still obtain numerical results for the PMV, the setting limit_inputs of the Python function has been set to unlimited [34]. External work is left, as default, as zero. The air

FIGURE 2: Distribution of the answers for ranges of temperature. Answers are plotted in different colours depending on in which temperature range they have been collected. The curve refers to the normal distribution.

velocity has been fixed at 0.1 m/s because, according to measurements in the monitored rooms, airspeed was never stronger than this value. As for dry bulb temperature and mean radiant temperature, we used the air temperature collected through the monitoring campaign. These last two approximations are based on the work of Alegría-Sala et al. [35], which proved that calculating the ASHRAE PMV without monitoring air velocity and mean radiant temperature was effective, with 100% of the cases falling within acceptable accuracy. Indeed, although ASHRAE recommends using the globe sensor to measure the mean radiant temperature, its error is $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, causing the PMV calculated with the air temperature to fall inside the range of the PMV calculated with the globe sensor [35].

The categories of the adaptive model have been calculated with the Python library `pythermalcomfort` [34]. External mean running temperatures have been calculated with

meteorological data downloaded from `meteo.cat` (station of El Raval), using the function `running_mean_outdoor_temperature` from the Python library `pythermalcomfort` [34], using an alpha of 0.8, as suggested by ASHRAE 55 2020 [29] (slow responding). The number of previous days used to calculate the outdoor running mean temperature is seven, as suggested by EN 16798-1 2019 [36].

Additionally, we calculated a new neutral temperature, defined as the indoor temperature which an average occupant finds neither warm nor cool [37], for both FITLOW and HIGH. The aim was to find new comfort ranges, as existing models are not suitable for this kind of building. The methodology followed is the one suggested by Vellei et al. [38], consisting of performing a simple linear regression of indoor temperatures acquired through field studies against the corresponding external mean running temperatures for TSV equal to zero (neutral temperatures). After

FIGURE 3: Blue dots represent the plotting of HSV against the relative humidity measured. Each graph corresponds to a different group of answers. The straight lines are the linear correlations between the HSV and relative humidity in each case. The red-shaded area is the 95% confidence band.

having performed this analysis, the study is aimed at comparing different comfort parameters (temperature, relative humidity, and heat index) and models (PMV and adaptive) with the sensations of occupants collected through the survey.

Finally, the methodology suggested by Vanos et al. [39] has been applied to the collected data to understand whether the monitored solutions might have an adverse effect on the health of occupants. Indeed, many metrics based on physiology have been applied to project heat stress. Sherwood and Huber [40] established 35°C of wet bulb temperature as a threshold that would result in death after 6 h of exposure. Considering that a human would experience death from hyperthermia in almost 100% of cases when their core temperature exceeds 43°C [41, 42], Vanos et al. [39] define the limit of survivability as reaching a core temperature of 43°C in 3- or 6-h exposure to allow for comparison with the wet bulb temperature of 35°C assumption (heat stroke death after 6 h). Liveability denotes the highest internal heat production or level of physical activity an individual can engage in without experiencing sustained positive heat storage in the current environmental conditions. Vanos et al. [39] applied a heat exchange model to the whole human body to estimate heat stroke deaths and maximum/safe activity intensity, focusing on two subpopulation types (younger (~18–30 years) and older (>65 years) female adults). The present work plotted the monitored environmental conditions

(combinations of temperature and humidity) against the survivability curves they identified.

3. Results and Discussion

As the main objective of this study is to get an idea of the comfort of occupants while doing some kind of sport, the results explain each comfort parameter used. In every case, a correlation is looked for between the sensations of the users from the interview and the objective data measured at the moment of the answer (a magnitude directly measured or a calculated index). The following graphs have the collected sensation on the horizontal axis (represented with a Likert scale) and the measured parameter on the vertical one. In graphs where TSV is analysed, the thermal sensation of the questionnaire in the form of a Likert scale has been simplified with numbers, where “0” is the *neutral sensation*, “-3” is “*very cold*,” and “+3” is “*very hot*.” When the humidity sensation value (HSV) is plotted, the Likert scale used was made up of only five points, so “0” is “*neutral*,” “-2” is “*dry*,” and “+2” is “*humid*.” A linear fit is proposed, together with its 95% confidence band, in shaded red.

Figure 1 shows the correlation between the TSV of the user and the air temperature of the rooms. In general, it is possible to see that there is a correlation between these two parameters, which means that people are averagely able to detect temperature and that temperature influences the

FIGURE 4: Blue dots represent the plotting of TSV against the heat index calculated. Each graph corresponds to a different group of answers. The straight lines are the linear correlations between the and relative humidity in each case. The red-shaded area is the 95% confidence band.

thermal sensation of people. The only case in which this correlation looks not significant is the case of FITLOW activities in summer, where the line is almost horizontal. Although the fitting lines of FITLOW and HIGH activities are not perfectly parallel, they have a similar tilt but a different intersection with the vertical axis. On average, there is between 1° and 1.5° (vertical) difference between the regression lines of winter FITLOW and winter HIGH data, while there is between 0.5° and 1° in summer.

Dividing the answers based on the range of temperature makes it possible to understand for which temperature most of the neutral answers have been received (Figure 2). The highest percentage of neutral answers has been collected in the winter HIGH group, with 62.5% of answers for temperatures lower than 21°C . The other peak is reached for winter FITLOW and temperatures lower than 21°C or between 22°C and 23°C . The maximum reached here is 40%. Looking at the summer period, there is a strong shift towards intense thermal sensation, and especially in HIGH activities, it looks difficult to be in a comfortable situation in almost every condition. Most of the occupants answered that they were feeling hot or that, in general, they had quite a strong thermal sensation.

The situation is much different for relative humidity, as shown in Figure 3. The correlation lines are almost horizontal, except for winter HIGH. It looks like people are not very sensitive to changes in the RH. Indeed, according to the literature review by Ganesh et al. [4], humans are not capable

of sensing humidity, as they do not have specific receptors for it but feel it indirectly using, for example, temperature receptors.

The following comfort parameter which has been investigated is the heat index, shown in Figure 4, which is a combination of temperature and relative humidity. In summer, for both FITLOW and HIGH, some answers are in the caution band ($27 < HI < 32$) according to the National Weather Service Heat Index derived by Lu and Romps [43, 44]. In winter HIGH, the linear fitting has a negative slope (opposite to the expected behaviour), which might be caused by the low number of points in this group. No strong correlation is found again.

Figure 5 instead provides a comparison between TSV and PMV. The linear fitting and the scatter of points plotted are very far from the line, having as coordinates $TSV = PMV$. For FITLOW, the model overestimates the thermal sensation when occupants have answered a thermal sensation lower than +1 and underestimates them above this value. For HIGH activities, all points are overestimated, meaning that this model is not suitable for being used with high metabolic rates, or more in general, for sports activities. The results show how, when doing sports, whether a low- or high-intensity activity and no matter the season, Fanger's model is not able to describe and foresee the thermal sensation of occupants.

Lastly, the analysis makes a comparison between the TSV of people and the adaptive comfort model. Figures 6

FIGURE 5: Blue dots represent the plotting of TSV against calculated PMV. Each graph corresponds to a different group of answers. The straight lines are the linear correlations between the TSV and PMV in each case. The red-shaded area is the 95% confidence band.

and 7 show the new neutral temperature calculated for FITLOW and HIGH (with indoor air temperature and external running mean temperature measured for answers with $TSV = 0$, as explained in the methodology). Light blue lines are the original adaptive model comfort category limits. In most cases, the answers fall into the neutral range or in the -1 original adaptive model comfort category. The FITLOW neutral temperature (Figure 6) is less steep than the original category limits, probably indicating lower adaptivity of the occupants when doing sports. The HIGH neutral temperature is very similar to the Category 1 lower limit. Once again, there is a vertical gap between these two lines for lower external running temperatures, which reduces as the external running temperature increases.

Finally, data recorded at the moments of the interview were plotted against the survivability curves identified by Vanos et al. [39] for younger and older female adults (see Figure 8). In the case of FITLOW activities (black dots), for both subpopulations, points are inside the liveability limit. In the case of HIGH activities (white dots), three points appear beyond the liveability limit for both subpopulations. The hypothesized MET is 6.8 in this case. If it was a young person doing it, they would be doing an activity of 6.8 MET when the maximum recommended for liveability under those combinations of humidity and temperature would be 5 MET. If it was an older female adult, they would be doing a 6.8 MET activity when the maximum is 3 MET.

4. Limitations and Further Research

Data collection has been done in spaces used by many people at a time for doing physical activities. If, on one side, it allows gathering data from real classes and users, on the other, it does not always allow placing the optimal number of sensors in the best locations.

Using an online tool introduces positive aspects to the making and results of the survey. The absence of an interviewer allowed the interviewee to feel more comfortable with their answer and not be influenced by anyone. At the same time, it reduced the time spent by researchers collecting data. Nevertheless, it increased uncertainty about the data in cases of misunderstanding or wrong interpretation of the questions. In future research, collecting a higher number of answers would allow for results with higher relevance.

The research did not consider all those parameters influencing the thermal comfort of people, such as weight, height, age, gender, and health status. A more detailed survey and data collection should be designed to also get this information and study its effect on the answers.

The research and its future development should focus on finding values that are not dangerous for the health of occupants and allow them to pursue energy savings. Realizing a model of the building's thermal behaviour, energy consumption, and thermal comfort of occupants and validating it through the collected data would allow us to test different

FIGURE 6: Neutral temperature calculated for FITLOW activities (green line). Points refer to answers to the survey and have been coordinated with the running mean temperature of the day they answered and the indoor temperature measured.

FIGURE 7: Neutral temperatures calculated for HIGH activities (green line). Points refer to answers to the survey and have been coordinated with the running mean temperature of the day they answered and the indoor temperature measured.

FIGURE 8: Estimates of liveability at varying combinations of air temperature and relative humidity under shaded conditions/indoors from Vanos et al. [39]. Black and white points refer to data collected during the monitoring campaign with temperature and relative humidity high enough to appear in this psychrometric graph.

situations and precisely calculate the design parameters for sports centres.

5. Conclusions

Temperature, among the monitored parameters, is the one with the highest influence on the TSV, while IEQ votes show poor sensitivity to variations of RH, although the measured RH is always in the range of recommended values for indoor activities. The heat index is not significantly correlated with the occupants' sensations. In the summer, a few answers were collected under the caution risk conditions.

A comparison of the two comfort models with the collected data reveals discrepancies. Fanger's model often mispredicts occupants' thermal sensations, with a calculated PMV differing significantly from the actual TSV, possibly due to high metabolic rates exceeding ASHRAE 55 limits. The adaptive comfort model also fails to accurately represent occupants' TSV, with many responses falling within the comfort or -1 range yet still experiencing discomfort. Even when identifying neutral temperature curves for low and high levels of activity (FITLOW and HIGH), the distinctions between comfort and discomfort for hot and cold sensations are minimal, with the graph showing close or even overlapping regions. Answers in summer FITLOW are all very close, i.e., collected with similar interior and exterior conditions, but still different from one another. In winter FITLOW, the points are a bit more dispersed, and the TSV looks like it mostly depends on the indoor temperature, while the external mean running temperature is less influential. This is reflected in a lower slope of the neutral

temperature line, which ultimately means lower adaptability for occupants.

It has not been possible to find optimal comfort conditions for the majority of people. While the peak of neutral sensation occurs at temperatures below 21°C for a minority (37.5%), higher temperatures result in most feeling "very hot." Occupants of the monitored sports centres mostly felt warm or even hot for temperatures higher than 21°C when doing sports.

Data compared to the results of models assessing human survivability [39] (see Figure 8) show that occupants have been exposed to unsafe conditions (accumulation of internal heat) during activities in the monitored rooms.

Nomenclature

HSV	humidity sensation vote
IEQ	indoor environmental quality
PMV	predictive mean vote
POE	postoccupational evaluation
TSV	thermal sensation vote

Appendix

List of the questions made in the online survey which are relevant to this study.

1. What clothes are you wearing? You can choose all the options that represent you.
 - Underwear
 - Short sleeve t-shirt

- Long sleeve t-shirt
 - Shorts
 - Long trousers
 - Underwear
 - Jumper
 - Knee-length skirt
 - Socks
 - Closed shoes
 - Sandals or open shoes
2. How do you rate your thermal sensation?
- Hot
 - Warm
 - Slightly warm
 - Neutral
 - Slightly cool
 - Cold
 - Very cold
3. How do you perceive the humidity level in the room?
- Humid
 - Slightly humid
 - Neither too humid nor too dry
 - Slightly dry
 - Very dry
4. How do you perceive the air movement in the room?
- Very low
 - Slightly low
 - Neither too low nor too high
 - Slightly high
 - Very high

Data Availability Statement

The environmental data and answers to the IEQ survey used to support the findings of this study have been deposited in the Zenodo repository (doi:10.5281/zenodo.10555619).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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References

- [1] P. O. Fanger, *Thermal Comfort*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1972.
- [2] Division of Statistics and Studies, Technical General Secretay, and Culture and Sports Ministry, *Statistics yearbook of sports statistics 2022 (ESTADÍSTICA ANUARIO DE ESTADÍSTICAS DEPORTIVAS 2022)*, GENERAL TECHNICAL SECRETARIAT General Subdirectorate of Citizen Services, Documentation and Publications, 2022.
- [3] L. Borghero, S. Escudero, J. Ortiz, J. Romaní, and E. J. Salom, "Review of comfort standards in weight and group fitness rooms and comparison with monitored and perceived data," in *27th International Congress on Project Management and Engineering Donostia-San Sebastián*, pp. 532–544, Spain, 2023.
- [4] G. A. Ganesh, S. L. Sinha, T. N. Verma, and E. S. K. Dewangan, "Investigation of indoor environment quality and factors affecting human comfort: a critical review," *Building and Environment*, vol. 204, article 108146, 2021.
- [5] Federal Facilities Council, *Learning from our buildings: A state-of-the-practice summary of Post-occupancy evaluation*, National Academies Press, 2002.
- [6] X. Huang, G. Chen, C. Zhao, Y. Peng, and E. W. Guo, "Post occupancy evaluation of indoor environmental quality of sports buildings at hot and humid climate from the perspective of exercisers," *Building and Environment*, vol. 226, article 109760, 2022.
- [7] R. J. De Dear, T. Akimoto, E. A. Arens et al., "Progress in thermal comfort research over the last twenty years," *Indoor Air*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 442–461, 2013.
- [8] P. O. Fanger, "Calculation of thermal comfort: introduction of a basic comfort equation," *ASHRAE Transactions*, vol. Part II 73, pp. III4.1–III4.20, 1967.
- [9] J. Van Hoof, "Forty years of Fanger's model of thermal comfort: comfort for all?," *Indoor Air*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 182–201, 2008.
- [10] W. C. Howell and P. A. Kennedy, "Field validation of the Fanger thermal comfort model," *Human Factors*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 229–239, 1979.
- [11] D. J. Croome, "Thermal comfort and air quality in offices," *Indoor Air*, vol. 6, 2010.
- [12] G. S. Brager and R. J. De Dear, "Thermal adaptation in the built environment: a literature review," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 83–96, 1998.
- [13] R. De Dear and G. S. Brager, "Developing an adaptive model of thermal comfort and preference," *ASHRAE Transactions*, vol. 104, no. Part 1A, pp. 145–167, 1998.
- [14] P. Li, T. Parkinson, S. Schiavon et al., "Improved long-term thermal comfort indices for continuous monitoring," *Energy Build*, vol. 224, article 110270, 2020.
- [15] R. De Dear, J. Xiong, and J. Kim, "A review of adaptive thermal comfort research since 1998," *Energy Build*, vol. 214, article 109893, 2020.

- [16] R. Shawesh and M. Mohamed, "Post-occupancy evaluation of outdoor thermal comfort in hot arid zone," *International Journal of Low-Carbon Technologies*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 50–60, 2021.
- [17] M. S. Alam, M. Sharma, and U. R. Salve, "Assessment of thermal comfort in a hot and humid indoor built environment of a kitchen at a university canteen," *Work*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 189–199, 2022.
- [18] M. S. Alam, A. Muthiah, and U. R. Salve, "Thermal comfort of the kitchen in pantry cars on Indian railways," *Instrumentation, Mesures, Métrologies*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 465–477, 2019.
- [19] S. I. Bengi and A. Y. Toprakli, "The perspective of Turkey in the post occupancy evaluation studies," *Periodica Polytechnica Architecture*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 83–91, 2020.
- [20] J. Ortiz, M. L. Gonzalez Matterson, P. Taddeo, and J. Salom, "Post-occupancy evaluation of indoor environmental quality in a nZEB sport hall in a Mediterranean climate," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 111, p. 02048, 2019.
- [21] G. M. Revel and M. Arnesano, "Measuring overall thermal comfort to balance energy use in sports facilities," *Measurement*, vol. 55, pp. 382–393, 2014.
- [22] G. M. Revel and M. Arnesano, "Perception of the thermal environment in sports facilities through subjective approach," *Building and Environment*, vol. 77, pp. 12–19, 2014.
- [23] A. Dudzińska, T. Kisilewicz, and E. Panasiuk, "Impact of material solutions and a passive sports hall's use on thermal comfort," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 23, p. 7698, 2023.
- [24] M. Kottek, J. Grieser, C. Beck, B. Rudolf, and F. Rubel, "World map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification updated," *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 259–263, 2006.
- [25] B. E. Ainsworth, W. L. Haskell, S. D. Herrmann et al., "2011 Compendium of physical activities," *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 1575–1581, 2011.
- [26] B. E. Ainsworth, W. L. Haskell, S. D. Herrmann et al., "2011 compendium of physical activities: a second update of codes and MET values," *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 1575–1581, 2011.
- [27] A. Alegria-Sala, E. Clèries Tardío, L. C. Casals, M. Macarulla, and J. Salom, "CO₂ concentrations and thermal comfort analysis at onsite and online educational environments," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 19, no. 23, p. 16039, 2022.
- [28] S. Alam, A. Muthiah, and U. R. Salve, "Appraisal of thermal comfort in non-air-conditioned and air-conditioned railway pantry car kitchens," *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 318–327, 2020.
- [29] ASHRAE Standing Standard Project Committee 55 and ASHRAE STANDARDS COMMITTEE 2020, *ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55-2020 Thermal Environmental Conditions for Human Occupancy*, ASHRAE, 2021.
- [30] D. Meyer and D. Thevenard, "PsychroLib: a library of psychrometric functions to calculate thermodynamic properties of air," *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 4, no. 33, p. 1137, 2019.
- [31] O. Travis, *Numpybook*, Trelgol Publ, USA, 2007.
- [32] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort et al., "Scikit-learn: machine learning in Python," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 12, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
- [33] L. P. Rothfus, *The heat index " equation " (or, more than you ever wanted to know about heat index)*, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Weather Service, Office of Meteorology, Fort Worth, Texas, 1979.
- [34] F. Tartarini and S. Schiavon, "Pythermalcomfort: a Python package for thermal comfort research," *SoftwareX*, vol. 12, article 100578, 2020.
- [35] A. Alegria-sala, D. M. Lopez, L. C. Casals, J. Fonollosa, and E. M. Macarulla, "The dilemma of variables assumptions in thermal comfort calculations for educational buildings: to simplify or not?," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 84, article 108404, 2024.
- [36] European Committee for Standardization, "Energy performance of buildings — Ventilation of buildings — Part 1: Indoor environmental input parameters for design and assessment of energy performance of buildings addressing indoor air quality, thermal environment, lighting and acoustics (Module M1–6)," vol. 44, 2019.
- [37] A. K. Mishra and M. Ramgopal, "Field studies on human thermal comfort - an overview," *Building and Environment*, vol. 64, pp. 94–106, 2013.
- [38] M. Vellei, M. Herrera, D. Fosas, and S. Natarajan, "The influence of relative humidity on adaptive thermal comfort," *Building and Environment*, vol. 124, pp. 171–185, 2017.
- [39] J. Vanos, G. Guzman-echavarria, J. W. Baldwin, K. L. Ebi, and O. Jay, "A physiological approach for assessing human survivability and liveability to heat in a changing climateA physiological approach for assessing human survivability and liveability to heat in a changing climate," *Nature Communications*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 7653, 2023.
- [40] S. C. Sherwood and M. Huber, "An adaptability limit to climate change due to heat stress," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 107, no. 21, pp. 9552–9555, 2010.
- [41] N. Christidis, D. Mitchell, and P. A. Stott, "Rapidly increasing likelihood of exceeding 50 °C in parts of the Mediterranean and the Middle East due to human influence," *NPJ Climate and Atmospheric Science*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2023.
- [42] A. Bouchama, B. Abuyassin, C. Lehe et al., "Classic and exertional heatstroke," *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 8, 2022.
- [43] Y. C. Lu and D. M. Romps, "Extending the heat index," *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, vol. 61, no. 10, pp. 1367–1383, 2022.
- [44] National Weather Service, *What is the heat index? National oceanic and atmospheric administration*, 2023, July 2024, <https://www.weather.gov/ama/heatindex>.